

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Analysis of Surface Coverage Loss Caused by Sensor Misplacement in 3D Triangulation Systems

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ABSTRACT This paper presents a quantitative analysis of the impact of inaccurate positioning (deviations in position and orientation) of a 3D triangulation scanner on surface coverage. Using simulated scanning of a publicly released dataset of 50 heterogeneous STL models, the ideal sensor position maximizing surface coverage was first identified for each object. Subsequently, the influence of spatial deviation and angular inaccuracy was systematically examined in this optimal configuration. The results show high sensitivity of the system, where even a small deviation in position (25 mm) leads to an average loss of coverage of 7.99 %, and in the case of geometrically complex objects with a high degree of self-occlusion, the degradation of data is statistically significantly higher, which was confirmed by statistical analysis using paired t-tests. Orientation analysis revealed that tilts around axes perpendicular to the viewing direction have a significantly more destructive impact than rotation around the viewing axis. The simulation results were validated by real measurements using a triangulation-based 3D scanner mounted on a robotic workstation, showing good agreement between simulated and real data. The proposed methodology and the obtained data provide a quantitative framework for defining scanner positioning tolerances in real-world industrial applications and for the design of robotic inspection cells.

INDEX TERMS 3D scanning, optimal sensor placement, sensitivity analysis, surface coverage, triangulation-based sensor, virtual inspection.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of industrial 3D scanning applications places increasing demands on measurement accuracy, repeatability, and overall process efficiency. In many industrial scenarios, 3D scanning is employed for product inspection, serving both as an end-of-line quality control tool and as an in-process inspection method during manufacturing [1]. 3D imaging sensors, ranging from their fundamental triangulation principles to their diverse applications in industrial and medical fields, have been extensively documented, highlighting their role as a mature technology for non-contact measurement [2]. Typical examples include machined components mounted in fixtures [3], cast parts extracted from molds, wood-processing applications [4], and

components produced by additive manufacturing, including 3D-printed polymer and concrete structures [5]. In such cases, the geometric configuration of the inspected part with respect to its surroundings is known, and the inspection process is often based on one or only a few fixed sensor viewpoints [6].

From the perspective of inspection quality, one of the key requirements is the maximization of the visible surface area of the object within a single measurement [7]. This criterion enables the definition of an optimal scanner position and orientation relative to the inspected part, achieving the highest possible surface coverage with a minimal number of sensors [8]. Such an approach is particularly advantageous in automated and time-critical applications, for example during in-process inspection in manufacturing environments.

Existing research has predominantly focused on scanner trajectory optimization [9], multi-view acquisition planning

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[8], the definition of the complete 3D model acquisition pipeline [10], or improvements in data segmentation algorithms [11]. Other studies have addressed the quality of data acquired by triangulation-based scanners as a function of surface properties [12], [13]. However, relatively little attention has been paid to a systematic sensitivity analysis of inaccuracies in placing the scanner at its optimal position, particularly in the context of geometrically complex objects exhibiting a high degree of self-occlusion. Yet, this sensitivity is of fundamental importance for the design of measurement fixtures, robotic manipulators, and positioning tolerances in automated inspection systems [14]. The selection of suitable scanner viewpoints is closely related to sensor planning problems studied in computer vision, where sensor parameters are determined to ensure visibility, measurement feasibility, and optimal coverage of the observed object [15], [16].

However, the practical problem remains of implementing this optimal configuration in a real environment. Placing the scanner in a precisely defined position and orientation requires either highly accurate positioning systems or reliable methods of external measurement of its position and orientation [17]. In the absence of sufficiently accurate measurement or calibration, inevitable positional and orientation errors occur when setting the scanner to its ideal configuration. These deviations can have a significant impact on the actual achievable surface coverage and thus on the quality of the resulting inspection.

This article focuses on a quantitative analysis of the impact of inaccurate positioning (deviations in position and orientation) of a triangulation 3D scanner in the optimal position on the size of the visible (triangulable) surface of an object. Using simulated scanning of 50 heterogeneous stereolithography (STL) models, the ideal sensor position maximizing surface coverage is first found for each object. Subsequently, the influence of the spatial deviation of the scanner from the ideal position and the influence of the angular inaccuracy of its orientation are systematically examined in this optimal configuration.

The proposed methodology enables separate evaluation of the system's sensitivity to positional and orientational errors and provides statistically supported conclusions across a wide spectrum of geometric shapes. The results of this study offer practically applicable insights for the design of robust 3D inspection processes and for defining scanner positioning tolerances in real industrial applications.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this study, a Python-based application was developed to simulate the scanning of 3D objects (STL models) using a triangulation scanner. The application is capable of evaluating the area of the scanned surface and, based on this evaluation, determining the camera position that maximizes the surface coverage of the scanned object. The entire algorithm for

estimating the size of the scanned surface can be divided into five main functional blocks, which together form a closed-loop optimization cycle for determining the sensor position with respect to the digital (STL) model.

- 1) Preprocessing and initialization: Loading the 3D geometry, generating a reference point cloud (P_{ref}) by uniform surface sampling, and computing surface normals.
- 2) Methodology for surface visibility and triangulability determination.
- 3) Evaluation: Assessment of the ratio of triangulable points to the total number of points (VisibleRatio).
- 4) Sensor position optimization strategy (grid search).
- 5) Analysis of the impact of sensor positioning inaccuracies relative to the ideal position.

A. METHODOLOGY FOR REFERENCE POINT CLOUD GENERATION

To enable an objective evaluation of surface visibility and triangulability, the surface of the polygonal mesh (STL) was transformed into a discrete set of reference points P_{ref} . To avoid bias caused by local variations in mesh density (i.e., triangle size), a uniform area sampling method was employed.

The point generation process is carried out in three stages, which ensure a constant point density over the entire surface regardless of the mesh topology:

- Area-based probability distribution: Each polygon (triangle) in the mesh is assigned a weight proportional to its area. The probability P_i that a point is generated within the i -th triangle is defined as

$$P_i = \frac{A_i}{\sum_{j=1}^M A_j}, \quad (1)$$

where A_i represents the area of the i -th triangle and M denotes the total number of polygons in the mesh. This step eliminates measurement bias that would otherwise occur in meshes with non-uniform triangulation.

- Barycentric Point Mapping: The actual position of a point within a selected triangle is determined using random parameters transformed into barycentric coordinates. For a triangle with vertices V_1, V_2 and V_3 , the point P is computed as

$$P = (1 - r_1) V_1 + (r_1 (1 - r_2)) V_2 + (r_1 r_2) V_3, \quad (2)$$

where r_1 and r_2 are random variables uniformly distributed in the interval $[0, 1]$. This formulation ensures that each point lies precisely in the plane of the element and that the distribution over the surface remains uniform.

- Computation of Surface Normal Vectors: Concurrently with the point positions, the surface normal vector n is determined for each sample. For accurate simulation of optical visibility, the orientation of these vectors

FIGURE 1. Surface coverage of a 3D model with a reference point cloud: (a) original 3D model, (b) triangular mesh, (c) model sampled with 5,000 points, (d) triangular mesh covered with 5,000 points.

is unified across the entire model to ensure they always point outward from the object. This alignment is essential for the subsequent calculation of the dot product between the sensor’s viewing vector and the surface orientation.

An example of a 3D model and its individual surfaces are illustrated in Fig. 1. It can be observed that the object’s surface is uniformly covered with points, even though the sizes of the individual faces in the 3D model vary significantly. Using the described method, the 3D model is sampled with 5,000 points.

The total number of generated points N (set to 500,000 in this study) was chosen as a compromise between computational cost and sufficient resolution for shadow (occlusion) detection, even for geometrically complex shapes. The resulting point cloud thus represents a digital twin of the surface, where each point carries information about its position in \mathbb{R}^3 and the orientation of the surface.

B. METHODOLOGY FOR DETERMINING SURFACE VISIBILITY AND TRIANGULABILITY

The computational model for determining the visibility of points on the object’s surface simulates the actual optical measurement process using a triangulation scanner. This approach is based on geometric principles of active 3D vision systems, where the spatial relationship between the light source and the receiver defines the sensor’s operational constraints [10]. A point on the surface is considered measurable (triangulable) only if the conjunction of visibility

conditions is satisfied for two independent optical systems: the camera (C) and the projector (P).

The evaluation process for each optical system is carried out in the following three sequential steps:

- 1) Field of View (FOV) Analysis: A point x in \mathbb{R}^3 must lie within the monitored volume of the optical system, which is defined as a frustum. This volume is determined by the intrinsic parameters of the system (horizontal angle α_H and vertical angle α_V) and its spatial transformation. A point is considered valid if its projection onto the sensor plane lies within the following bounds

$$-\tan\left(\frac{\alpha_H}{2}\right) < \frac{x_s}{z_s} < \tan\left(\frac{\alpha_H}{2}\right), \tag{3}$$

$$-\tan\left(\frac{\alpha_V}{2}\right) < \frac{y_s}{z_s} < \tan\left(\frac{\alpha_V}{2}\right), \tag{4}$$

where (x_s, y_s, z_s) are the coordinates of the point in the local sensor coordinate system, with z_s representing the depth of the point relative to the optical center.

- 2) Surface Orientation Analysis (Normal Test): This phase evaluates the orientation of the surface relative to the viewing direction. In order for the surface to reflect a light beam toward the sensor, it must face the sensor. This condition is expressed using the dot product between the viewing direction vector \mathbf{d} and the outward unit surface normal \mathbf{n} at the given point

$$\mathbf{d} \cdot \mathbf{n} < 0. \tag{5}$$

If the result is positive, the point is back-facing and is considered invisible to the given optical system.

- 3) Self-Occlusion Detection (Occlusion Test): The final step is to verify whether any part of the object’s geometry lies between the optical center of the system and the test point P . This step is implemented using a raycasting method. From the optical center O , a ray is cast in the direction of the point P . The algorithm detects the nearest intersection of this ray with the model surface, denoted as P_{hit} . The point P is considered as visible only if

$$\|P_{hit} - O\| \geq \|P - O\| - \epsilon, \tag{6}$$

where ϵ is a small tolerance factor used to eliminate numerical instabilities when the ray hits the surface. Otherwise, the point is classified as occluded.

The final classification of a point as “triangulable” is conditional on its simultaneous visibility from both the camera and the projector. This binary state is represented by the mask $M(P)$

$$M(P) = V_c(P) \cap V_p(P), \tag{7}$$

where V_c and V_p are the results of the visibility tests for the camera and the projector, respectively.

As shown in Fig. 2, the triangulation scanner and the point cloud on the surface of the scanned component

FIGURE 2. Triangulation scanner view: green – emitter FOV, magenta – camera FOV; red – visible points, blue – occluded points.

are illustrated. Points that are triangulable are colored in red, while points that are not triangulable are shown in blue.

The proposed methodology for determining surface visibility and triangulability is based on several simplifying assumptions. In particular, the optical system is assumed to be ideal, and visibility is modeled as a binary condition, meaning that a surface point is considered either visible or not visible. Effects such as lens distortion, sensor calibration errors, diffraction, sensor noise, lighting conditions, surface reflectivity, and material properties are not explicitly modeled. These assumptions simplify the geometric analysis and reduce computational complexity. However, they also mean that the model does not fully represent real-world imaging conditions. Therefore, the presented results should be interpreted with these limitations in mind.

C. COMPUTATION OF THE TRIANGULABLE SURFACE AREA

The main indicator of the quality of a given sensor position is the visible surface ratio R_{vis} , which is defined as the ratio of the number of triangulable points N_{tri} to the total number of reference points N_{total}

$$R_{vis} = \frac{N_{tri}}{N_{total}} = \frac{1}{N_{total}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{total}} M(P_i). \quad (8)$$

This coefficient directly correlates with the percentage of the object’s surface covered in a single measurement and serves as an objective function for optimizing the sensor’s position in space.

D. SENSOR POSITION OPTIMIZATION STRATEGY (GRID SEARCH)

Due to the nonlinear nature of the visibility function in a complex workspace, a multi-stage grid search method was chosen to find the global maximum. This process transforms the continuous space of possible sensor positions into a series

of structured grids that reflect the geometric characteristics of the task. The chosen method is based primarily on the need for a systematic and complete search of the workspace, which ensures that no relevant area is overlooked. At the same time, it is an approach that is relatively simple to implement and easily replicable.

Compared to random sampling methods and optimization-based approaches (e.g., Monte Carlo, Genetic Algorithms, or Particle Swarm Optimization), the proposed strategy follows a deterministic and systematic procedure. Although this approach may, in certain cases, require greater time and computational resources, it was preferred because it guarantees that the entire discretized search space is evaluated. Optimization algorithms typically have the advantage of converging efficiently toward an optimal solution. However, they may converge to a local optimum rather than the global one, which was the main reason for preferring the systematic grid-based search in this work [18].

1) GLOBAL SEARCH USING A CYLINDRICAL GRID

In the first phase, the workspace is defined as a hollow cylinder surrounding the measured object. This approach simulates real-world scenarios in which the sensor (e.g., mounted on a tripod) is positioned around the object within a certain range of heights and distances. The position in the grid is discretized using three parameters:

- Azimuthal Angle: Defines the rotation around the vertical axis of the object.
- Vertical Level: Defines the height of the sensor above the base.
- Radial Distance: Specifies the distance of the sensor from the axis of rotation.

At each position of this grid, the sensor is automatically oriented so that its optical axis points toward the centroid of the object. The result is a rough visibility map that identifies areas that are candidates for global maximum.

2) LOCAL REFINEMENT USING A SPHERICAL GRID

After identifying the most suitable position from the cylindrical grid, the local refinement phase follows. In the immediate vicinity of the point P_{best} a dense spherical grid is constructed. At each point of this grid, the sensor is oriented toward the centroid of the object. This process precisely localizes the global maximum C_{opt} , which serves as the starting point for further analysis. The spherical grid is defined by:

- Center position: The center of the grid, corresponding to the candidate sensor position C_{opt} .
- Target position: The point toward which the sensor is oriented, corresponding to the object centroid.
- Radial range: Defined by the minimum and maximum radius, limiting the admissible distance of the sensor from the center position.

- Number of radial layers: The radial dimension is discretized into a fixed number of concentric layers.
- Angular discretization: The spherical surface is discretized using a fixed number of meridians and parallels.

For each configuration C_i (defined by its position and orientation), the value $R_{vis}(C_i)$ is computed. The optimal configuration C_{opt} is then defined as the maximum over this discrete set

$$C_{opt} = \arg \max_{i \in \text{grid}} \{R_{vis}(C_i)\}. \quad (9)$$

E. ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF SENSOR POSITIONING INACCURACIES RELATIVE TO THE IDEAL POSITION

Once the ideal position C_{opt} , has been determined, the impact of geometric inaccuracies on data quality is investigated under two separate scenarios:

- Spatial Deviation (Spherical Error Grid): Concentric spherical layers with different radii are defined around the optimal position C_{opt} . These radii represent positioning errors of the sensor's optical center. Within each layer, sensor positions are generated with an orientation that maintains the viewing direction toward the object centroid, thereby isolating the effect of pure positional error.
- Orientational Deviation (Rotational Variation): The position of the optical center is fixed at C_{opt} and the algorithm performs iterative tilts about the local x -axis and y -axis. This scenario simulates inaccuracies in the angular placement of the sensor. In this manner, the effect on the visible surface area can be evaluated independently

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This section describes the simulation parameters and the characteristics of the dataset used for the statistical validation of the impact of positioning errors on the quality of 3D scanning.

A. STL DATASET

To ensure the statistical robustness of the results, 50 heterogeneous STL models were included in the study. Sample of 25 of them are illustrated in Fig. 3. The dataset was constructed to cover a wide range of geometric characteristics:

- Simple geometries: Convex objects without internal structures (e.g., prisms, spheroids).
- Industrial components: Mechanical parts with holes, grooves, and recesses.
- Complex topologies: Organic shapes and models with deep cavities exhibiting a high degree of self-occlusion.

Prior to generating the reference point cloud, the models were exported to the STL format using a consistent geometric tolerance. Their sizes were constrained to fit within a cube with an edge length of 500 mm, while also being sufficiently large so as not to fit within a cube with an edge length of 100 mm. The coordinate systems of all models were aligned

FIGURE 3. Sample of 25 STL models out of the 50 used in the study.

with the object centroids to enable straightforward import into the virtual scanning scene.

Subsequently, each model was converted into a reference point cloud with a density of 500,000 points using the uniform area sampling method. The dataset containing all 50 STL models is available in the Zenodo public repository [19].

B. SCANNER MODELING

The simulated sensor is based on the principle of a structured-light triangulation scanner. It consists of a camera and a projector with defined parameters, such as the camera field of view, the projector field of view, and their mutual separation. The parameters of the virtual scanner used in the experiments were derived from the real-world Photoneo PhoXi M scanner. The individual 3D scanner parameters employed in the simulation are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Simulation parameters of the 3D scanner.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Camera Horizontal FOV	47.5	deg
Camera Vertical FOV	36.4	deg
Emitter Horizontal FOV	47.5	deg
Emitter Vertical FOV	36.0	deg
Camera-Emitter Distance	354.75	mm

C. METHODOLOGY FOR OPTIMAL CONFIGURATION SEARCH AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

The process of determining the optimal sensor position and subsequently evaluating the impact of scanner positioning inaccuracies was performed separately for each 3D model according to the following steps:

- 1) Global phase: Exploration of the workspace using a cylindrical grid surrounding the object.

TABLE 2. Grid parameters for global search, local refinement, and sensitivity analysis.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Global Search: Cylindrical Grid		
Min. radius	500	mm
Max. radius	800	mm
Height	700	mm
Number of azimuthal samples	20	–
Number of vertical samples	10	–
Number of radial samples	5	–
Total number of grid positions	1000	–
Local Refinement: Spherical Grid		
Min. radius	10	mm
Max. radius	200	mm
Number of radial layers	20	–
Number of meridians	10	–
Number of parallels	10	–
Total number of grid positions	2000	–
Positional sensitivity Analysis: Spherical Grid		
Min. radius	25	mm
Max. radius	500	mm
Number of radial layers	20	–
Number of meridians	20	–
Number of parallels	20	–
Total number of grid positions	8000	–
Orientation sensitivity Analysis: Orientation Grid		
Rotation range (X, Y, Z)	±30	deg
Rotation step (X, Y, Z)	3	deg
Total number of orientations	9261	–

- 2) Local phase: Refinement of the sensor position in the vicinity of the identified maximum using a dense spherical grid.
- 3) Positioning error sensitivity analysis: Generation of test spherical layers with radii (25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175, 200, 225, 250, 275, 300, 325, 350, 375, 400, 425, 450, 475, 500) mm around the computed optimum. The triangulable surface area is evaluated at each position.
- 4) Orientation error sensitivity analysis: Generation of test orientations at the computed optimum position. The triangulable surface area is evaluated for each orientation.

The configuration parameters of the individual grids are summarized in Table 2. The parameters for each grid were selected based on the limitations of the Photoneo scanner and as a compromise between the level of detail in the exploration of the entire space and the computation time.

To eliminate numerical errors during ray–surface intersection, a tolerance factor of $\epsilon = 10^{-4}mm$ was applied.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the results of the sensitivity analysis of surface coverage with respect to sensor positioning errors, based on the processing of data from 50 test STL models.

A. SENSITIVITY TO POSITION ERRORS

The evaluation process was based on the analysis of relative changes in the amount of acquired data as a function of deviations from the optimal scanner position. For each

FIGURE 4. Percentage coverage loss by distance from ideal position.

tested object, a reference configuration with the highest absolute percentage of surface coverage was first identified during the optimal position search and its subsequent local refinement.

Subsequently, for all positions within the spherical error grid, the differences in surface coverage relative to this ideal value were computed. These relative changes were statistically aggregated for each tested distance from the optimum. This procedure enabled an accurate assessment of the decrease in percentage surface coverage as a direct function of sensor positioning inaccuracies. This relationship is visualized in Fig. 4.

The measured data reveal the following observations:

- High initial sensitivity: A notable finding is the abrupt degradation observed already at the smallest tested deviation of 25 mm, where the average loss reaches 7.99 % and the upper adjacent value is 21.69 %. This indicates that, for geometrically complex models, even very small positioning errors are critical due to increased self-occlusion.
- Gradual increase in degradation: After the initial drop, the average error increases more gradually. Between deviations of 25 mm and 500 mm, the average degradation nearly doubles (from 7.99 % to 15.01 %). This suggests that while small positioning errors primarily lead to the loss of fine details and narrow cavities, larger errors result in the significant occlusion of entire object surfaces.
- Asymmetry of the distribution: Across all measurements, the mean value exceeds the median (e.g., at 500 mm, the mean is 15.01 % compared to a median of 12.87 %). This positive skewness confirms the presence of a subset of models with high geometric complexity, which disproportionately increase the mean due to their extreme sensitivity to positioning errors.

To support the claims of statistical significance, a statistical analysis was performed on the surface coverage loss data obtained for different positional deviations from the optimal scanner position. The analysis was performed on aggregated

datasets containing surface coverage loss values from all STL models and all evaluated scanner poses for each tested positional deviation. Since the values for different distances were obtained from the same dataset evaluated under different positional deviations, the samples are not independent and were therefore treated as paired samples. For this reason, paired two-sample t-tests were used to compare the mean surface coverage loss between consecutive positional deviations (e.g., 25 mm vs. 50 mm, 50 mm vs. 75 mm, etc.). The significance level was set to $\alpha = 0.05$.

The null hypothesis H_0 assumed that there is no difference between the mean surface coverage loss values for two compared positional deviations, i.e., the positional deviation does not influence the surface coverage loss. The alternative hypothesis H_1 assumed that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean values.

The statistical tests showed statistically significant differences between surface coverage loss values for all compared positional deviations. The calculated t-statistics ranged within the interval $t(19999) \in (-15.26, -5.47)$, with all corresponding p -values below 0.001. Therefore, the null hypothesis H_0 was rejected for all tested positional deviations, confirming that positional inaccuracies have a statistically significant effect on the visible surface coverage of the scanned object.

B. SENSITIVITY TO ORIENTATION ERRORS

This subsection analyzes the sensitivity of surface visibility to orientation inaccuracies of the scanner. The evaluation was performed by fixing the optical center at the optimal orientation and subsequently tilting the scanner within a range of $\pm 30^\circ$ with a step of 3° independently around the x , y , and z axes.

Tilts around the x and y axes (corresponding to horizontal and vertical scanner inclinations) exhibit a symmetric and highly steep degradation of surface coverage, as illustrated in Figs. 5 and 6.

- x and y axes: Within the tilt range from 3° to 12° , an approximately linear decrease in visible surface area can be observed. At a tilt angle of 15° , the average reduction in surface coverage reaches 15.39 % for the x -axis and 11.36 % for the y -axis. At the maximum tilt of 30° , the mean loss exceeds 33 %, while for the most sensitive models (upper adjacent value) more than 52 % of the data are eliminated. In many cases, this corresponds to the loss of nearly the entire originally visible surface.
- z -axis: Rotation around the viewing axis demonstrates significantly higher robustness. Across the entire range of $\pm 30^\circ$, the average loss of surface coverage remains consistently below 10.5 %.

The abrupt loss of visible surface area observed for tilts around the x and y axes (approximately at 15°) is primarily caused by the displacement of the scanned object outside the field of view of the triangulation-based scanner.

FIGURE 5. Percentage coverage loss caused by angular offset around the sensor x -axis from the optimal orientation.

FIGURE 6. Percentage coverage loss caused by angular offset around the sensor y -axis from the optimal orientation.

FIGURE 7. Percentage coverage loss caused by angular offset around the sensor z -axis from the optimal orientation.

- **FOV:** Since the half field-of-view angles of the simulated camera are approximately 23.75° horizontally and 18° vertically, any sensor tilt exceeding these values causes parts of the object to exit the observable volume. Although the object’s centroid—toward which the scanner is oriented in the optimal configuration—may remain within the image, the peripheral regions of the object leave the sensor’s field of view.
- **Triangulation:** Because a 3D point must be simultaneously visible to both optical subsystems (the camera and the projector) to be triangulated, it is sufficient for the object to exit the field of view of only one of them. As the sensor is tilted, the overlap of their respective fields of view is progressively reduced, leading to a rapid loss of triangulatable surface.

To provide a comprehensive assessment of the combined influence of tilts around the x and y axes, a heatmap of the

FIGURE 8. Heatmap – Average percentage coverage loss of visible area compared to angular deviations around x-axis and y-axis.

average surface coverage loss was generated (see Fig. 8). The plot clearly identifies a central stability region, where small angular deviations (approximately up to $\pm 6^\circ$) result in minimal loss of visible surface area, remaining below 6–8 %.

The visualization further reveals a region of abrupt change in surface visibility (approximately at tilt angles between 15° and 18°), where the scanned object is progressively displaced outside the scanner’s field of view.

A statistical analysis was performed to evaluate the significance of differences in surface coverage loss caused by angular deviations of the scanner around the x , y , and z axes. Paired two-sample t-tests were used to compare the mean surface coverage loss between consecutive angular deviations (e.g., 0° – 3° , 3° – 6° , etc.). The analysis was performed on aggregated datasets containing surface coverage loss values from all STL models and all evaluated scanner orientations for each tested angular deviation. The significance level was set to $\alpha = 0.05$. The null hypothesis H_0 assumed that there is no difference between the mean surface coverage loss values for two consecutive angular deviations, while the alternative hypothesis H_1 assumed that a statistically significant difference exists.

For rotations around the x -axis, statistically significant differences were observed for angular intervals 0° – 3° , 9° – 12° , 12° – 15° , 15° – 18° , 18° – 21° , and 21° – 24° . For these intervals, the calculated t-statistics ranged within the interval $t(49) \in \langle -6.69, -2.47 \rangle$ with p -values below 0.015. The remaining angular intervals (3° – 6° , 6° – 9° , 24° – 27° , and 27° – 30°) were not statistically significant, with p -values above 0.17 and t-statistics in the interval $t(49) \in \langle -1.38, -0.68 \rangle$.

For rotations around the y -axis, statistically significant differences were observed for angular intervals 0° – 3° , 12° – 15° , 15° – 18° , 18° – 21° , 21° – 24° , 24° – 27° , and 27° – 30° . For these intervals, the calculated t-statistics ranged within

the interval $t(49) \in \langle -8.56, -3.61 \rangle$ with p -values below 0.001. The remaining angular intervals (3° – 6° , 6° – 9° , and 9° – 12°) were not statistically significant, with p -values above 0.24 and t-statistics in the interval $t(49) \in \langle -1.17, -0.39 \rangle$.

For rotations around the z -axis, statistically significant differences were observed only for angular intervals 0° – 3° and 21° – 24° , where the calculated t-statistics ranged within the interval $t(49) \in \langle -6.19, -2.14 \rangle$ with p -values below 0.04. The remaining angular intervals (3° – 6° , 6° – 9° , 9° – 12° , 12° – 15° , 15° – 18° , 18° – 21° , 24° – 27° , and 27° – 30°) were not statistically significant, with p -values above 0.1 and t-statistics approximately within the interval $t(49) \in \langle -1.32, 1.54 \rangle$.

Based on the statistical tests, the null hypothesis H_0 was rejected for angular intervals where $p < 0.05$ and could not be rejected for intervals where $p \geq 0.05$. The statistical analysis therefore confirms that angular deviations around the x and y axes have a statistically significant effect on surface coverage mainly when the object begins to leave the scanner field of view, whereas rotations around the z -axis have a considerably smaller and often statistically insignificant effect on the visible surface coverage.

C. HARDWARE CONFIGURATION AND EXECUTION TIME

All experiments were conducted on a workstation equipped with an AMD Ryzen 9 9950X processor, 64 GB of RAM, and an NVIDIA GTX 5090 GPU with 32 GB of VRAM. The average processing time for a single STL model was measured across all 20,261 evaluated sensor configurations, encompassing the cylindrical grid search, local refinement using the spherical grid, positional error analysis in the spherical grid, and orientation error analysis in the angular grid. With the STL surface uniformly sampled into a reference point cloud of 500,000 points, the total computation time per model amounted to 739 seconds on average. The duration of the computation time is directly proportional to the number of positions checked and the number of sampled points.

D. EVALUATION WITH REAL SCANNER

To verify the proposed methodology for virtual scanning, experimental measurements were conducted using a real triangulation 3D scanner. The aim of the experiment was to compare the results of the simulated scan with the data obtained from the actual measurement, with the scanner positioned identically in both the simulation and the real-world environment. For verification, one of the objects (bench vise) used in the virtual scanning simulations was selected (see Fig. 3). Using the same object in both the simulation and the real measurement ensured consistency of the evaluation and allowed direct comparison of the results.

The experimental measurements were conducted at a robotic workstation equipped with a UR10e collaborative robot, which was used to accurately position and orient the 3D scanner in predefined poses corresponding to the simulation. A Photoneo PhoXi M 3D scanner was mounted on the robot

as the end-effector. The scanned object was placed within the robot's workspace and suspended from the workstation frame using transparent fishing line so as to minimize the impact of the mounting on the visibility of the object's surface while ensuring that no significant parts of the model were covered. This verification setup of the robotic workstation is shown in Fig. 9.

FIGURE 9. Scanned object on workplace with scanner mounted on robotic arm.

The coordinate system of the scanned object was defined in the same way as in the simulation. The robot, equipped with the 3D scanner, moved sequentially to predefined positions that corresponded to the positions used in the scanning simulation. At each position, a 3D scan of the object was performed, and a point cloud representing the scanned surface area was obtained. From each scan, a polygonal mesh was created representing the actually scanned portion of the object's surface for the given scanner position.

The size of the scanned surface area was determined by calculating the total area of the polygonal mesh obtained from the scan. The surface area was computed as the sum of the areas of individual triangles forming the mesh:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^N S_i, \tag{10}$$

where S_i is the area of the i -th triangle and N is the total number of triangles in the mesh. This area was then compared with the total surface area of the original STL model of the object. The ratio of these areas represents the real scanned surface coverage of the object. This parameter was then compared with the value obtained from the simulated scanning.

The experimental verification was performed in the vicinity of the optimal scanner pose determined by the virtual scanning optimization. The scanner was placed in the optimal position and subsequently rotated around its local x , y , and z axes in the range of $\pm 30^\circ$ with a step of 3° . These orientations corresponded to the scanner poses used in the simulation, and

the comparison between simulation and real measurements was performed for these poses.

For each angular offset, a real scan was performed and the scanned surface area was calculated. The loss of scanned surface coverage relative to the optimal orientation was then computed and compared with the results obtained from the virtual scanning simulation. The comparison between simulated and real measurements for rotations around the x , y , and z axes is shown in Fig. 10, Fig. 11, and Fig. 12.

FIGURE 10. Comparison of surface coverage loss caused by angular offset around the sensor x -axis from the optimal orientation for simulation and real scan.

FIGURE 11. Comparison of surface coverage loss caused by angular offset around the sensor y -axis from the optimal orientation for simulation and real scan.

FIGURE 12. Comparison of surface coverage loss caused by angular offset around the sensor z -axis from the optimal orientation for simulation and real scan.

The experimental verification was further performed for scanner poses with positional offsets from the optimal

scanner position. The scanner was moved along straight lines passing through the optimal scanner position. The positional offsets were evaluated along the x -axis and z -axis of the object coordinate system. The scanner poses corresponding to the positional offsets along the x -axis and z -axis are visualized in Fig. 13.

FIGURE 13. Visualization of scanner poses along the x -axis and z -axis. Local coordinate systems indicate scanner orientation.

For each offset position along the x -axis and z -axis, a real scan was performed and the scanned surface area was calculated. The loss of scanned surface coverage relative to the optimal position was then evaluated and compared with the results obtained from the virtual scanning simulation.

The comparison of surface coverage loss caused by positional offsets along the x -axis and z -axis is shown in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15. The results show a similar trend between the simulation and real measurements, confirming that the simulation model is able to predict the influence of positional deviations on the scanned surface coverage.

FIGURE 14. Comparison of surface coverage loss caused by positional deviation from the optimal scanner position in x -axis.

FIGURE 15. Comparison of surface coverage loss caused by positional deviation from the optimal scanner position in z -axis.

FIGURE 16. Reconstructed mesh from real scanning with visible reconstruction artifacts and floating blob-like artifacts in space.

For individual scanner positions, the surface coverage ratios obtained from simulation and real measurements were compared. The results show that the simulated model is able to predict the changes in scanned surface coverage depending on the scanner position and orientation with relatively good agreement.

Certain differences between the simulation and real measurements were observed. In the real scans, small reconstruction artifacts appeared, mainly around sharp edges and object boundaries. Additionally, several isolated artifacts in the form of small blob-like clusters were observed in free space, which did not correspond to the actual object geometry. These artifacts slightly increased the surface area of the reconstructed mesh, which resulted in a small overestimation of the scanned surface area in the real measurements. An example of the reconstructed mesh with visible artifacts is shown in Fig. 16.

Further differences are caused by simplifying assumptions of the simulation, particularly the ideal optical model, binary visibility model, sensor noise, material reflectivity, and calibration inaccuracies of the real system.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a virtual inspection methodology focused on analyzing the sensitivity of triangulation-based

3D scanning to inaccuracies in sensor position and orientation. Based on simulated scanning of fifty heterogeneous STL models, an optimal scanner configuration maximizing the triangulatable surface area was first identified. This configuration subsequently served as a reference point for a systematic evaluation of the impact of geometric deviations.

In real-world applications, the criterion of maximizing total visible surface area may not always be relevant. In many industrial scenarios, only specific functional regions of manufactured parts need to be inspected. In such cases, the proposed methodology allows the reference point cloud to be restricted to inspection-critical surface regions only. The optimal scanner position can then be determined by maximizing the visibility of this reduced set of reference points. Importantly, the proposed algorithm can be applied without any structural modifications; only the set of evaluated reference points differs.

The results demonstrate that the system exhibits high sensitivity even to relatively small positioning errors. A deviation of only 25 mm from the optimal position already leads to a non-negligible average reduction in visible surface area, while for geometrically complex objects the degradation can be extreme. This finding confirms that precise scanner positioning is particularly critical when scanning objects with deep cavities, holes, and pronounced self-occlusion.

The analysis of orientation inaccuracies further revealed that tilts around axes perpendicular to the viewing direction (x and y) have a strongly detrimental effect on surface coverage, whereas rotations around the viewing axis (z) are comparatively robust. The critical threshold values of angular deviations are closely linked to the limited fields of view of the camera and projector and to the requirement of their simultaneous visibility for successful triangulation.

To support the statistical significance of the observed differences in surface coverage loss between individual positional and angular deviations, statistical analysis using paired t-tests was performed. The results confirmed that the differences between the evaluated configurations are statistically significant in most tested cases. Furthermore, the simulation results were validated by real measurements using a triangulation-based 3D scanner mounted on a robotic workstation, and good agreement between simulated and real data was observed.

The presented study provides a quantitative framework for defining positioning tolerances of 3D scanners and highlights the importance of accurate sensor orientation in practical applications. The results can serve as a basis for optimizing measurement fixtures, robotic trajectories, and automated inspection systems where high measurement reliability and repeatability are required.

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